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INHALT:

H. Hass

Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Reteporiden

unter Berücksichtigung der Formbildungsgesetze ihrer Zoarien und
über die dabei angewandte neue Methode für Untersuchungen
auf dem Meeresgrund

Mit 10 Tafeln sowie 63 Abbildungen im Text und auf 4 Beilagen

ZOOLOGICA

101:

An Important,
But Largely Forgotten

Document in the
History of Scientific Diving

E. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung
(Erwin Nägele)

Hans Hass's ZOOO

Hass investigated the growth laws of reteporids in his thesis.

Images courtesy Michael Jung, The Hans Hass Institute

LOGGICA 101:

An Important, But Largely Forgotten Document in the History of Scientific Diving

By Michael Jung

Despite major technical, physiological, and psychological obstacles, humans tried early on to gain more knowledge about the underwater world. Coastal free divers were the first humans to dive into the sea many thousands of years ago in search of food such as snails, shells, and seaweed, and to collect pearls, coral, and sponges. They brought the first empirical findings and knowledge from the underwater world. Until the 20th century, only very few scientists dived into the depths with diving bells or helmet diving suits. Diving was still very risky and laborious. There was no well-founded knowledge about the behavior of sharks on humans, and the correct use of helmet diving equipment had to be learned first. Not every scientist was physically capable of diving with this heavy equipment. The open diving helmets used by William Beebe, for example, were the first step forward, but still had many disadvantages.

This situation only changed when lightweight, autonomous diving equipment came onto the market. In combination with rubber fins, they not only made diving much more comfortable, but also much easier to learn. It was now possible to explore areas that were previously inaccessible, such as underwater caves, wrecks, and steep walls.

Hans Hass with the oxygen diving apparatus and mask in Greece in 1942.

Pioneering Methods

The Austrian diving pioneer Hans Hass was, in 1942, the very first scientist who developed and used this new research method and opened this new path to scientific diving. He used a Draeger Oxygen rebreather, rubber fins, and a mask for his dives. In doing so, he ushered in a new era of three-dimensional scientific scuba diving.

According to Riccardo Cattaneo-Vietti and Angelo Mojetta, this autonomous diving with light equipment as a research method now plays an “essential role” in marine biology, opening up “unexpected horizons in science” and thus ushering in a scientific revolution: “The direct access to underwater habitats determined a scientific revolution, by allowing a considerable advancement of the marine world’s knowledge and constituting an approach that no surface-operated instrument can ever match.”

In his book, *Men and Sharks* (Jarrolds, 1954), Hass reported in detail on the events of the 1942 expedition, which led from July to November 1942 through the Aegean Sea near Greece and to the coast of Crete. On July 14, 1942, he used the new diving equipment for the first time on the small Greek island of Argyronisos (“Silver Island”). As he wrote in his book, he was overwhelmed with emotion. He felt like a “Christmas angel” flying over the undersea landscape. “Uncontrolled delight took possession over me.

Never had I felt so free and unhampered under water as I did with this gear. I could take whatever position I pleased. I could sit down or lie down or turn somersaults or stand on my head; here was no clumsy diver groping along the ground, but a new sort of amphibious being swimming as the sea had never seen anything swim.”

Perilous Dangers

Diving with oxygen equipment was very dangerous, as there was still no precise knowledge of the depth at which oxygen becomes toxic. During the expedition, there were two accidents, which Hass survived only by sheer luck.

The Austrian diving pioneer Hans Hass was, in 1942, the very first scientist who developed and used this new research method and opened this new path to scientific diving. He used a Draeger Oxygen rebreather, rubber fins, and a mask for his dives. In doing so, he ushered in a new era of three-dimensional scientific scuba diving.

Hass studied zoology at the University of Berlin during these years. During the expedition, Hass collected “moss animals” (Bryozoa) in various underwater locations. They belong to a group of animals that includes several thousand species, some of which are bizarrely shaped. Similar to a coral reef, these structures are made up of countless tiny polyps. Which of these thousands of species did this bryozoan from Greece belong to, or was it perhaps an as-yet unknown species? Hans Hass had suddenly found the topic for his doctoral thesis: He wanted to investigate how this perfect network that made up the bryozoans was formed and uncover the secret of their growth laws.

During the expedition, Hass was able to observe and film sharks underwater that had been attracted by dynamite fishermen. These film recordings are now of great scientific value, as they are the only way to determine which shark species used to live in Greek waters.

In November 1942, after more than four months in Greece, Hans Hass arrived back in Berlin and began his investigations under the microscope. He had brought a total of almost 1,500 specimens with him. It was important for further work to carry out further investigations under water. Hass, therefore, traveled to the zoological station in Naples in the spring of 1943.

The Threat of War

The greatest difficulty here was obtaining the official permits for diving and photographic work in the Gulf of Naples. It was not until the beginning of July that Hans Hass was able to make his first dive descent on the small rocky island off Massa Lubrense. Further dives followed, for example, in the Blue Grotto of Capri and the rock gate of the first Faraglioni Island.

The worsening war situation forced Hans Hass to prematurely abandon the investigations he had begun, and he moved to the Institute of Oceanography in Rovinj, Yugoslavia. Here he only had the opportunity to make a single dive descent. Due to the delicate political situation at the time, Hass had to return after just three days.

Further work was then completed over the next few months in Berlin and at the Zoological Institute of the University of Vienna. Hass was supported in some of his work by two students. They were Rupert Riedl, who later became known as an evolutionary researcher, and his friend, Ernst Rille. Both had already experimented with self-made diving equipment and underwater cameras in Lake Wörthersee, then heard that Hass had fled Berlin before the bombing raids and was now continuing his work in Vienna. Without further ado, they introduced themselves to him.

Doctoral Recognition

On February 23, 1944, Professor Ludwig Bieberbach, Dean of the Friedrich Wilhelm University in Berlin, presented Hass with his certificate of appointment as Doctor rer. nat. with the distinction “summa cum laude.” This coveted distinction had not been awarded to a zoologist at the university for eight years and recognized Hans Hass’s extraordinary achievements. He had succeeded in tracing the growth laws of reteporids back to mathematical laws. This doctoral thesis is still regarded today as a milestone in zoological research, as it was the first scientific work to be carried out by a free-diving person with the aid of a self-contained diving apparatus.

The movie *Men and Sharks* was made during the expedition in Greece.

With the autonomous diving device and fins, steep walls can also be examined for the first time.

Hass observed and filmed sharks and other creatures underwater.

This doctoral thesis was not published as a printed book until 1948, because the end of the war and the collapse of Germany did not allow it to be published earlier. The thesis was published as part 101 of the series *Zoologica* under the title, "Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Reteperiden. Mit besonderer Berücksichtigung der Formbildungsgesetze ihrer Zoarien und einem Bericht über die dabei angewandte neue Methode für Untersuchungen auf dem Meeresgrund" (Contribution to the knowledge of reteporids. With special consideration of the laws of form formation of their zoaria and a report on the new method used for investigations on the seabed).

Hass's Vision of the Future

In the first chapter of this 140-page dissertation, Hass also gives a detailed report on the new method of underwater research using autonomous diving equipment and the new possibilities it offers for science. At the end of his dissertation, Hass recommends that in future every marine biology station should train a few assistants as swimming divers. "If a specialist then arrives - and these are mostly older gentlemen - then such a biologist trained as a diver can certainly provide valuable services, provided that the occurrence of the forms to be studied is not limited to too great a depth. However, it would be best if the researchers in question were to use the new method themselves." Hass's vision has now been realized, and three-dimensional Scientific Scuba Diving has become an integral part of underwater research. 🐠

Investigations on bottom vegetation.

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